

X-Ray, electrical, infrared and catalytic studies of the system $Zn_xCu_{1-x}Ga_2O_4$

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The system $Zn_xCu_{1-x}Ga_2O_4$ has been studied with a view to investigating the cation distribution and to correlate the catalytic behaviour of spinel with electrical and structural properties. The catalytic evaluation has been carried out in the temperature range 200–400° using benzyl alcohol as a probe molecule. The results show $CuGa_2O_4$ to be better catalyst for benzyl alcohol decomposition compared to $ZnGa_2O_4$.

We have reported spin-glass nature of gallium containing spinel ferrites¹, magnetic, transport and spectroscopic studies of nickel-gallium ferrites², and electrical, transport, magnetic and catalytic studies of the system $Ga_{1-x}FeCuMnO_4$ ³. A good correlation has been established between structural and catalytic activity of the mixed metal oxide system. Several workers have reported electrical conductivity, crystallographic, magnetic and spectroscopic studies of gallium containing compounds^{4,5}. Gallium containing spinels have been investigated for nitrous oxide decomposition⁶ and dehydrogenation of 1-octanol³, while pure Ga_2O_3 has been reported as an effective catalysts for decomposition of methyl cyclohexanol⁷. However, no work is reported on decomposition of benzyl alcohol using gallium containing catalysts. We have investigated the effect $Zn_xCu_{1-x}Ga_2O_4$ with a view to investigating the system of substitution of Zn^{II} ions on structural and electrical properties and its subsequent effect on catalytic activity towards benzyl alcohol decomposition.

Results and Discussion

Structural analysis : The results of X-ray analysis (Table 1) reveal that lattice constant increases from $CuGa_2O_4$ ($a = 8.310$ Å) to $ZnGa_2O_4$ ($a = 8.362$ Å) obeying Vegard's law. The increase in the lattice constant is due to replacement of smaller Cu^{II} (i.r. = 0.72 Å) by comparatively bigger Zn^{II} ion

Table 1. Lattice constant (a), activation energy (ΔE), thermoelectric coefficient (∞), for the different compositions of system $Zn_xCu_{1-x}Ga_2O_4$

Composition	a	ΔE	∞
X	Å	eV	$\mu V/K$
0.0	8.310	0.39	-26.0
0.25	8.320	0.40	-20.0
0.50	8.331	0.45	-05.0
0.75	8.340	0.47	+15.0
1.0	8.362	0.50	+33.0

(i.r. = 0.74 Å). The lattice constant observed for the compositions $X = 0.0$ and 1.0 are in close agreement with the values reported earlier⁴.

To arrive at the cation distribution and its variation with the composition, intensity ratios I_{220}/I_{400} and I_{440}/I_{422} for various possible models of cation distribution for the compositions $X = 0.5$ was calculated and compared with the observed intensity ratios. The results are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of intensity ratios for $Zn_{0.5}Cu_{0.5}Ga_2O_4$

Cations at		I_{220}/I_{400}	I_{440}/I_{422}
A-site	B-site	Calc.	Calc.
$Cu_{0.5}^{2+}Zn_{0.5}^{2+}$	Ga_2^{3+}	1.06	1.82
$Cu_{0.3}^{2+}Ga_{0.7}^{3+}$	$Ga_{1.3}^{3+}Zn_{0.5}^{2+}Cu_{0.2}^{2+}$	1.15	2.06
$Ga_{1.0}^{3+}$	$Cu_{0.5}^{2+}Zn_{0.5}^{2+}Ga_{1.0}^{3+}$	1.20	2.95
$Ga_{0.5}^{3+}Cu_{0.5}^{2+}$	$Ga_{1.5}^{3+}Zn_{0.5}^{2+}$	1.27	3.42
$Zn_{0.45}^{2+}Ga_{0.3}^{3+}Cu_{0.25}^{2+}$	$Cu_{0.25}^{2+}Zn_{0.05}^{2+}Ga_{1.7}^{3+}$	1.37	3.88
$Zn_{0.3}^{2+}Ga_{0.6}^{3+}Cu_{0.1}^{2+}$	$Zn_{0.2}^{2+}Ga_{1.4}^{3+}Cu_{0.4}^{2+}$	1.49	4.00
$Zn_{0.5}^{2+}Ga_{0.5}^{3+}Cu_{0.2}^{2+}$	$Ga_{1.7}^{3+}Cu_{0.3}^{2+}$	1.542 ^a	4.14 ^b

^aObserved 1.543. ^bObserved 4.144.

Transport studies :

The room temperature resistivity (ρ_{RT}) values of all the compounds of the system were found to vary between 10^4 and $10^{11} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ for different values of X . High resistivity values indicate that the elements with only one oxidation state are present at B-site. The plot of $\log \rho$ vs $10^3/T$ showed a linear nature obeying Wilson's law,

$$\rho = \rho_0 \exp(\Delta E/KT)$$

From Table 1, it is observed that the activation energy increases with increasing value of X in the system. The increase in the activation energy with increasing values of X in the system is due to the fact that with the substitution of Zn^{II} ions in the lattice of $CuGa_2^{2+}O_4$, there is decrease in the number of Cu^{II}/Cu^I ion pairs resulting in decrease in the

conductivity and increase in activation energy for electron conduction. In addition, the Zn^{II} (d^{10}) orbitals are more contracted as compared to Cu^{II} or Ga^{II} (d^9). The decreased overlap with the oxygen $2p$, $3d$ and $4s$ orbitals of B-site ions has an indirect but appropriate effect on the hopping process at octahedral site.

The thermoelectric coefficient values for the different compositions of the system varied between -26.0 and $+33$ $\mu V/K$. The Seebeck coefficient values (α) are summarised in Table 1. From Table 1, it is observed that the copper-rich compositions are n -type, while zinc-rich compositions are p -type semiconductors. N -type behaviour of Cu-rich compositions can be explained on the basis of valency exchange mechanism where as copper hops between $+2$ and $+1$ oxidation states. However, presence of Cu^I could not be detected by XRD technique as its concentration might have been very small. Further presence of Cu^I can not be overruled as otherwise compounds would have shown insulating behaviour. P -type nature of Zn-rich compositions may be due to loss of some Zn^{II} ions during firing process, as a result small fraction of B-site cations might go to A-site creating holes in B-site, giving rise to p -type semiconduction. Such a possibility of loss of Zn^{II} during firing process has also been reported earlier⁸.

Infrared studies : The different compounds of the system showed two strong bands at around 600 and 420 cm^{-1} and a comparatively weaker band at around 326 cm^{-1} . The band positions and threshold frequencies for different compositions of the system are listed in Table 3. The threshold frequency is for electronic transition. It is found to increase with increasing values of X in the system which is in accordance with the trend observed for the activation energy for electron conduction (Table 3). The band positions for the compounds with $X = 0.0$ and 1.0 are in close agreement with the values reported earlier^{3,9} for gallium containing spinels. Predhomme and Tarte⁹ observed that in normal spinels both the absorption bands depend on nature of octahedral ions and not significantly depend on nature of tetra-

hedral ions. However, Waldron¹⁰ attributed the higher frequency band ν_1 at around 600 cm^{-1} to the stretching vibrations of octahedral groups and the band ν_2 at around 420 cm^{-1} to the vibrations of tetrahedral groups. In the present investigation, ν_1 is assigned to the stretching vibrations of tetrahedral M-O while ν_2 at around 420 cm^{-1} to octahedral M-O stretching vibrations. A comparatively weaker band ν_3 at around 326 cm^{-1} is attributed to lattice vibrations as a whole.

It is observed from Table 3 that for the substitution of Zn^{II} ions in the place of Cu^{II} in the lattice of $CuGa_2O_4$ both the stretching vibrations ν_1 and ν_2 shift from 613.9 to 580.4 cm^{-1} and 414.9 to 431.9 cm^{-1} , respectively. The change in the stretching vibrations at octahedral and tetrahedral sites is due to the fact that in $CuGa_2O_4$, A-site is occupied by Ga^{III} (i.r. = 0.61 A), hence the bonding force at A-site is more. With the subsequent replacement of Cu^{II} by Zn^{II} ions (i.r. = 0.74 A) an equal amount of Ga^{III} ions migrate from A-site to B-site as observed from X-ray intensity calculations, as a result of which total bonding force at tetrahedral as well as octahedral sites decreases hence the frequency of stretching vibrations shifts from 613.9 to 580.4 cm^{-1} and 414.9 to 431.9 cm^{-1} . Similar observation in the shift of band positions with the change in cation distribution has also been reported earlier³.

Catalytic studies : Catalytic dehydrogenation is a useful method for the preparation of aldehydes and ketones from primary and secondary alcohols, respectively¹¹. We investigated earlier the decomposition of benzyl alcohol using $CdFeCrO_4$ - $CuFeCrO_4$ and $ZnMnFeO_4$ - $CuMnFeO_4$ catalysts¹², and established a good correlation between cation distribution transport properties, magnetic nature and catalytic behaviour.

Catalytic decomposition of benzyl alcohol gave benzaldehyde and toluene as major products and benzene and methanol as minor products :

Here H^* = Adsorbed hydrogen.

The catalytic performance data for the oxidative dehydrogenation of benzyl alcohol is given in Table 4. It is observed that copper-rich compounds are more active compared to zinc-rich compounds at all temperatures. The decreased catalytic activity towards benzyl alcohol decompo-

Table 3. IR bands and threshold frequencies for the different compositions $Zn_xCu_{1-x}Ga_2O_4$

Composition	Absorption bands (cm^{-1})			Threshold frequency
	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	
X				
0.0	613.9	414.9	326.0	932.7
0.25	613.0	417.2	326.0	965.6
0.50	590.4	426.9	326.5	1014.1
0.75	584.8	422.0	326.0	1055.0
1.0	580.4	431.9	326.0	1100.0

Table 4. Catalytic performance data for the oxidative dehydrogenation of benzyl alcohol over the different compositions of the system

Composition	Temp. °C	% Conv.	% Selectivity		
			Benzaldehyde	Toluene	Other products
0.0	200	40.5	82.3	12.3	2.0
	300	54.5	76.1	18.5	3.1
	350	69.2	60.9	32.6	3.4
	400	81.8	52.8	45.5	1.2
0.25	200	25.1	87.1	07.3	2.2
	300	39.0	80.7	13.3	3.3
	350	52.1	75.2	21.7	2.8
	400	62.0	62.4	33.5	2.4
0.50	200	13.1	91.2	03.5	2.5
	300	25.4	88.0	08.6	1.3
	350	32.8	81.4	15.0	2.0
	400	44.5	70.1	24.4	3.4
0.75	200	9.1	94.3	00.6	3.0
	300	13.0	90.1	05.5	2.6
	350	21.3	88.7	07.5	1.8
	400	31.2	81.2	15.2	2.2
1.0	200	02.0	98.5	-	0.8
	300	03.5	95.7	-	1.5
	350	11.0	90.0	03.8	2.3
	400	25.2	85.1	07.5	1.9

sition of the system $Cu_{1-x}Zn_xGa_2O_4$ with increasing values of x can be explained on the basis of cation distribution and electrical properties of spinels.

The effect of activation energy on alcohol decomposition is shown in Fig. 1a. It is seen that with increasing values of activation energy benzyl alcohol decomposition decreases. At 350°, $ZnGa_2O_4$ ($\Delta E = 0.50$ eV) gave only 11.0% conversions, while at the same temperature $CuGa_2O_4$ ($\Delta E = 0.39$ eV) gave 69.2% conversion. Similar results have also been reported during the decomposition of isopropyl alcohol over $MgAl_{2-x}Fe_xO_4$ system¹³.

The effect of lattice constant on benzaldehyde selectivity is depicted in Fig. 1b. It is observed that with increasing lattice constant, benzaldehyde selectivity increases and toluene selectivity decreases. Lattice constant is directly related with the M-O bond length which in turn is related with the bond strength. Smaller the value of lattice parameter, stronger is the bond and hence the exchange lattice oxygen with substrate becomes difficult which otherwise favours oxidation (dehydrogenation) of alcohol. Similar observation was also reported in the investigation of decom-

Fig. 1. Plots (a) ΔE vs % conversion at 200°; (b) lattice constant vs dehydration and dehydrogenation selectivity.

position of isopropyl alcohol over magnesium aluminate¹³.

Conclusion : The studies reveal the following conclusions. (a) From X-ray intensity calculations, the probable cation distribution of the system can be suggested as $Zn_x^{2+}Ga_{1-x}^{3+}(Cu_{1-x}^{2+}Ga_{1+x}^{3+})O_4$. (b) Copper-rich compositions are n -type while zinc-rich are p -type semiconductors. (c) Copper gallet is the most selective dehydration catalyst while zinc gallet the most selective dehydrogenation catalyst, compared to the other oxidic compounds towards benzyl alcohol decomposition.

Experimental

The different compositions of the system $Zn_x-Cu_{1-x}Ga_2O_4$ where ($X = 0.0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75$ and 1.0) were prepared by mixing high purity oxides (A.R.), viz. Ga_2O_3 (99.9%), CuO (99.99%) and ZnO (99.99%) in appropriate molar ratios. Oxide mixtures were homogenised in acetone for 4 h. Pellets of the oxide catalysts were prepared using 2% polyvinyl acetate solution. 2 g of oxide mixture was taken for preparing pellet. The pellets were heated slowly in air for 15 h (1 K/min) in order to remove the binder and then heated at 1173 K for 48 h.

X-Ray diffraction patterns of oxide catalysts were recorded on a Siemens-D 500 Krystalloflex diffractometer with

microprocessor controller using Ni-filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. X-Ray patterns of all the compositions indicated formation of single spinel phase.

To measure the intensity, area under different (hkl) peaks were calculated and the value obtained in relation to the peak for 311 reflections was taken to be 100. The atomic scattering powers for various ions were taken from literature¹⁴. To determine the cation distribution and its variation with the composition, the intensity ratios I_{220}/I_{400} and I_{400}/I_{422} for different possible models of cation distribution were calculated as the reflections 220, 400, 440 and 422 are more sensitive towards cation distribution in the present system and then compared with the observed intensity ratios.

DC resistivity of mixed metal oxide compounds was determined using two-probe technique. The end faces of each pellet were coated with a thin layer of conducting silver paste and the resistivity was measured from room temperature to 773 K. Thermoelectric power measurements were carried out from room temperature to 573 K.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR 1600 spectrophotometer.

Catalysis : Each compound of the system was studied for its catalytic activity in the temperature range 200–400° using fixed bed flow reactor. The reactor was (25 cm × 10 mm id) made from pyrex glass. Powdered oxide catalysts (2.0 g) was held between two glass-wool plugs surrounded by glass beads to facilitate heat exchange. Benzyl alcohol was used as probe molecule. It was distilled before use and its purity checked by GC. The substrate was fed into the reactor with the help of motor driven syringe pump to ensure constant flow rate. The products were condensed using

dry ice/acetone traps and simultaneously analysed on gas-chromatograph. The products were further confirmed using authentic samples and by GCMS.

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